

**DEVELOPMENT OF MANAGERSAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE VOCATIONAL
EDUCATION SPECIALISTS: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS**

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Annotation. The article reveals the concept of "managerial competence" as a key component of the professional training of future vocational education teachers. The current challenges of its development are analyzed, including lack of practical experience, theoretical dominance, and low student motivation. Based on the results of an empirical survey of students in specialty 015 Professional education (by specializations), the level of formation of managerial skills and relevant educational needs is presented. The article substantiates the importance of applying innovative teaching methods—training sessions, case studies, simulations, project-based learning, and mentoring. Practical recommendations for improving the educational process to develop a high level of managerial culture among future professionals are offered.

Keywords: managerial competence; professional competence; formation of managerial competence; professional training; future teachers; training; case studies; project-based learning; simulations; mentoring; educational process; practical training.

**Розвиток управлінської компетентності у майбутніх фахівців професійної освіти:
проблеми та перспективи**

Анотація. У статті розкрито зміст поняття «управлінська компетентність» як ключової складової професійної підготовки майбутніх педагогів професійної освіти. Проаналізовано сучасні проблеми її розвитку, зокрема брак практичної складової, домінування теоретичного підходу, недостатню мотивацію студентів. На основі результатів емпіричного дослідження серед здобувачів спеціальності 015 Професійна освіта (за спеціалізаціями) висвітлено рівень сформованості управлінських умінь та актуальні освітні потреби. Обґрунтовано доцільність застосування інноваційних

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методів навчання — тренінгів, кейсів, симуляцій, проєктної діяльності, наставництва. Запропоновано практичні рекомендації щодо удосконалення освітнього процесу з метою формування високого рівня управлінської культури у майбутніх фахівців.

Ключові слова: управлінська компетентність; професійна компетентність, формування управлінської компетентності, професійна підготовка; майбутні педагоги; тренінги; кейси; проєктна діяльність; симуляції; наставництво; освітній процес; практична підготовка.

Introduction

The modern system of higher education in Ukraine is increasingly focused on developing key competencies that are essential for the successful professional activity of future specialists. Among them, managerial competence holds particular significance in the context of the dynamic development of the educational environment. For future vocational education teachers, managerial competence is not only an additional component of professional training but also a fundamental basis for the ability to effectively organize the educational process, coordinate instructional and production activities, make informed decisions, and foster a favorable environment for students' development[1; 2].

The importance of this topic stems from the need to update the content of vocational education, integrate modern managerial approaches into pedagogical practice, and ensure that the training of future specialists meets the demands of the labor market. Although managerial competence is formally recognized as an integral part of a teacher's professional readiness[6], its development during higher education remains insufficient. Current challenges include the predominance of theoretical instruction over practice and the limited use of interactive teaching methods. In addition, students often lack motivation toward managerial activities and have restricted opportunities to engage in real management situations during their studies.

This article aims to analyze the theoretical foundations, current state, challenges, and prospects for the development of managerial competence in future vocational education teachers.

The concept of "competence" in management science emerged as the role of employees in organizations expanded. In his work *Principles of Scientific Management*, F. Taylor linked employees' skills to their positions and to the development of their professional qualifications [15].

According to V. Ternopil'ska, managerial competence is formed on the basis of a specialist's value orientations, which shape their ability for professional self-development and foster career advancement [12].

A review of domestic and international studies[2; 3; 4] shows that the effective development of managerial competence relies on competence-based, learner-centered, and activity-oriented approaches. Modern pedagogy places particular emphasis on active learning methods, including project work, case studies, training sessions, simulations, and mentoring. However, in the preparation of future vocational teachers in Ukraine, the adaptation of these methods to the specifics of the educational environment, available technical resources, and students' individual characteristics remains a pressing issue.

Scholars define managerial competence as a multidimensional personal and professional construct that integrates knowledge, practical skills, abilities, value orientations, and personal qualities. Together, these elements ensure the effective performance of managerial functions and the conscious selection of behavioral strategies [13]. In contemporary research, managerial competence is further interpreted as a complex integrative formation that combines professional knowledge, practical skills, value orientations, and individual traits. Such a structure enables effective performance of managerial activities and supports the deliberate choice of appropriate behavioral models.

Results

To assess the current state of managerial competence formation among future vocational education specialists, a survey was conducted among students of specialty 015 “Vocational Education (by specializations)” at Lviv Polytechnic National University. The study involved 38 participants, including both bachelor's and master's students.

The survey examined students' subjective perception of the importance of managerial competence, their readiness to perform managerial functions, the sources of relevant skill development, and the barriers that hinder competence formation during studies. Notably, most respondents (about 80%) reported having some organizational or managerial experience (such as student leadership, project coordination, or event moderation), which indicates an initial readiness for a managerial role.

When asked about the importance of managerial competence for professional activity, more than 88% of respondents gave a positive response, demonstrating a high level of awareness of its value among future teachers. However, self-assessment of readiness to perform managerial functions on a 5-point scale ranged from 1 to 5, reflecting considerable variation in competence levels. A significant share of students (around 40%) rated themselves as “partially ready,” thereby acknowledging the need for further preparation.

The most frequently mentioned sources of managerial skill formation were participation in projects (72%), practical classes (67%), self-learning (44%), and lectures or seminars (33%). Training and mentoring were mentioned least often, which confirms their insufficient integration into the learning process. At the same time, most respondents expressed strong interest in the introduction of managerial training sessions, simulations, and case studies—66% considered them mandatory, while another 28% viewed them as at least desirable as elective courses.

The main obstacles to competence development identified by students included a lack of practice, an overload of theoretical content, the absence of real-life examples, and low student motivation. These findings indicate that even when relevant courses are available, without interactive methods and real-life applications, it is impossible to achieve an adequate level of managerial readiness.

Overall, the study results demonstrate a high level of student interest in the managerial component of the profession and several significant issues: excessive formalization of preparation, a lack of practical content, and insufficient use of modern methodological tools. This highlights the need to update approaches to vocational education in the context of managerial competence formation.

In the context of ongoing educational transformation and growing demands on vocational education professionals, traditional approaches to developing managerial competence are losing effectiveness. The dominance of lectures, limited practice opportunities, and reliance on rote reproduction of knowledge do not foster the acquisition of skills necessary for real managerial activity [1; 2]. In this regard, innovative teaching methods that actively engage students in management situations are becoming increasingly important [3; 5].

Among the most promising approaches is project-based learning, which integrates theory and practice, emphasizes student autonomy, and develops planning, coordination, decision-making, and teamwork skills. Participation in projects enables students to perform managerial functions under conditions that approximate professional practice. Consistent with the survey findings, project participation (72% of responses) was recognized by students as the most effective source of managerial skill development.

Case studies also demonstrate high effectiveness, as they are based on the analysis of concrete management situations. Their use fosters critical thinking, analytical ability, evaluation of possible actions, and justification of managerial decisions [3]. Importantly, case studies should be adapted to the realities of vocational education and the specific professional context of teachers.

Simulation modeling is likewise of great value for managerial competence development, as it recreates management processes within the framework of learning activities (e.g., simulated meetings, pedagogical councils, conflict resolution, or planning educational events) [4]. Such exercises allow students to practice leadership, decision-making under uncertain conditions, and direct participation in management tasks. According to the survey, 66% of respondents considered simulations and training sessions a mandatory part of professional preparation.

Mentorship is an equally important component, whereby experienced educators or project supervisors guide students during practice or assignments, transferring not only knowledge but also managerial experience. This form of interaction fosters reflective thinking, responsibility, and a conscious attitude toward management. While only a few students identified mentorship as an active tool, it is widely recognized in European pedagogical practice as one of the most effective methods for preparing future leaders of the educational process [5].

Innovative methods should not simply supplement the core curriculum but be fully integrated into it. They need to be embedded in vocational disciplines (e.g., Fundamentals of Educational Management, Pedagogical Mastery, Theory and Methodology of Vocational Training) as well as in practical training. Such integration would ensure a continuous trajectory of competence formation from the early years of study through to graduation [6].

Thus, the effective application of innovative teaching methods is key to the successful development of managerial competence among vocational education students. These methods not only enhance motivation but also provide authentic experiences essential for future professional self-realization in a complex and dynamic educational environment [7].

However, several challenges limit the effectiveness of this process. Most educational programs in Ukraine remain heavily theoretical, with only limited opportunities for practical assignments [8]. As a result, students acquire knowledge but lack sufficient opportunities to apply it in real managerial contexts, which reduces their preparedness for professional practice.

Another challenge lies in the timing of managerial courses, which are often introduced only in the later stages of study. For instance, Fundamentals of Educational Management and Project Management are typically offered toward the end of bachelor's or master's programs. This delay hinders gradual skill development and weakens integration of managerial competencies throughout the educational trajectory.

Additionally, many programs lack clear criteria for evaluating managerial competence, making it difficult to track student progress and discouraging self-reflection. The absence of systematic feedback, combined with limited use of interactive methods such as case studies, simulations, and role-playing, further undermines effectiveness [9].

Student motivation to develop managerial skills is also not consistently high. Some perceive these skills as secondary or relevant only for administrative roles in education, which decreases engagement and negatively influences learning outcomes.

To address these issues, specific pedagogical conditions must be created that combine theoretical understanding with practical experience [10]. First, managerial courses should be integrated throughout all stages of study rather than introduced only in later years. Early and consistent inclusion ensures systematic competence development and adaptation to real educational contexts [11].

Second, practical methods should be prioritized. Programs should actively use case studies, simulations, role-playing, and project-based work, enabling students to engage directly with realistic managerial scenarios. This approach fosters critical thinking and provides a safe environment to practice managerial skills without real-world consequences. Simulation technologies further strengthen this practice-oriented focus.

Third, mentorship should be systematically developed. Experienced teachers can guide students throughout their professional growth, offering not only theoretical knowledge but also

practical insights. Such mentorship creates a supportive educational environment where students can grow through individualized guidance and constructive feedback.

Finally, students should be encouraged to engage in self-reflection and self-assessment of managerial competencies. Evaluation systems must be transparent, comprehensive, and encompass both theoretical knowledge and practical skills, enabling continuous improvement through the identification of strengths and weaknesses.

Conclusions

The analysis of theoretical frameworks, empirical findings, and current educational practice confirms that managerial competence is a key component of vocational education teachers' professional preparation. Despite its formal recognition, actual competence levels among students remain uneven and are largely shaped by curriculum content, practical opportunities, and teaching methodologies.

The survey of specialty 015 Professional education (by specializations), students revealed strong awareness of the importance of managerial skills but also highlighted barriers such as the dominance of theoretical learning, insufficient practical focus, limited real-life management experience, and low motivation among some learners.

Innovative methods—including project-based learning, case studies, simulations, training sessions, and mentorship—are perceived as highly effective tools for competence formation. Their systematic integration can create a practice-oriented environment that fosters leadership, communication, and effective decision-making in response to educational challenges.

Based on the study results, the following practical recommendations are proposed:

- strengthen curricula by enhancing practical components;
- integrate innovative methods into vocational disciplines;
- implement mentorship systems within teaching practice;
- expand cooperation with employers to ensure practical exposure to managerial activities.

Therefore, the development of managerial competence in future vocational education teachers should be prioritized within modern professional education, ensuring the preparation of competitive, proactive, and leadership-oriented specialists in the field of education.

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